
Edo State Federal Inland Revenue Services Staff's Views on Digital Taxation and Sustainable Economic Development

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Abstract

The researchers investigated the effect of digital taxation on sustainable economic development. A survey research design was adopted while simple random sampling technique was employed to administer structured questionnaire to one-hundred (100) staff of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) in Edo State, Nigeria. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and simple linear regression correlation were used to analyse the data. The empirical findings showed that digital taxation has a significant effect on sustainable development. The researchers recommended that the government of Nigeria should consider the digitalisation of the tax system and administration for contributing immensely to sustainable development of the economy.

Keywords: Benefit Received Theory of Taxation, Digital Taxation, Sustainable Economic Development and Taxation

Introduction

Digital taxation is a new phenomenon for the digitalisation of the tax system through innovative means for enhancing sustainable economic development in Nigeria. A digital taxation economy focused mainly on non-resident company (NRC) for the effective usage of technology in the administration, collection and payment of tax by the relevant stakeholders and tax payers. An economy may be seen as the way a resource of a given society is distributed among the people living in the society (Grimsley, 2018, cited in Yakubu & Kadiri, 2019; Aslam & Shah, 2020). However, a country may experience an economic growth without the economy been developed, depending on the level of development of a country and the technological advancement of such a country the two words can be viewed differently.

Economic development is the problem of underdeveloped countries and economic growth to those of developed countries. The raising of income levels is generally called economic development. The identification and development of a gap followed by the will and effort to seize existing opportunities are essential to the entrepreneurial process through the process of digital communication (Rajamohan & Sathish, 2020). Lyla (2021)